

Comorbidity Burden and Sex as Key Determinants in Healthcare Utilisation in Chronic Wound Care - A Retrospective Observational Cohort Study

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Abstract

Background: Chronic wounds represent a significant challenge for healthcare and the individuals affected, impacting physical and mental well-being and leading to social deprivation and financial burdens. The study aimed to describe the comorbidity burden and sex disparities in healthcare utilisation of patients with chronic wounds in Austria.

Methods: We linked the electronic health records from an outpatient wound clinic with billing and reimbursement data from the Austrian Health Insurance Fund and examined aetiology, comorbidity burden, and healthcare utilisation patterns in patients with chronic wounds. Furthermore, we conducted a disaggregated sex analysis of the findings.

Results: A total of 3,847 patients with chronic wounds were included. Of these, 47.8% were female. Over two-thirds (71.6%) of those patients insured by the Austrian Health Insurance Fund were exempt from prescription charges, indicating socio-economic vulnerability. Except for chronic venous insufficiency (15.4% in females versus 10.6% in males), men had a significantly higher prevalence of diabetic foot syndrome (20.5% in males versus 14.7% in females), endocrine, nutritional or metabolic diseases (54.1% in males versus 43.9% in females) and diseases of the circulatory system (29.9% in males versus 22.6% in females). The frequencies differed most between the sexes in chronic peripheral arterial occlusive disease (25% in males versus 14.4% in females), polyneuropathy (30% in males versus 19.6% in females) and amputations (18% in males versus 8.2% in females). It was also observed that men visited the centre more frequently than women.

Conclusions: Understanding sex disparities and gender differences in patient health and healthcare trajectories is essential for patient-centred interventions. Early diagnosis, wound care through a multidisciplinary team approach, health promotion, and particularly early preventive care for men's health are imperative to improve healthcare outcomes. Furthermore, providing timely and accessible wound care to low-income populations is required.

Keywords

Chronic Wounds, Sex and Gender Disparities, Healthcare Utilisation Patterns, Prevention, Social Determinants of Health, Intersectionality

Background

Chronic wounds are defined as wounds that do not heal, i.e. do not achieve a sustainable anatomical and functional result within 2 to 12 weeks [1-4]. Underlying diagnoses include chronic peripheral venous insufficiency of lower extremities (CVI), chronic peripheral arterial occlusive disease (PAD), diabetes and polyneuropathy, and spinal cord injuries or immobility, which can lead to pressure ulcers [1]. The predominant aetiological factors of leg ulcers are venous, arterial, or arteriovenous in nature [5, 6]. Atypical wounds may account for up to 20% of all wounds, and many of these are likely to be underdiagnosed [7, 8]. The most common of these atypical ulcers are due to inflammatory causes, including vasculitis and pyoderma gangrenosum, vasculopathic and haematological conditions, infectious diseases, neoplastic factors, iatrogenic effects, and drug-induced aetiologies [8-10]. Genetic factors, radiation exposure, or immune system dysfunction can also play a role in the pathogenesis of chronic ulcers [1].

Chronic wounds lead to pain, unpleasant odours, reduced mobility, a heightened risk of infection and sepsis, along with limitations in daily activities and social participation. It is, therefore, associated with a great loss of health-related quality of life [11, 12]. Moreover, the need for regular treatment has significant implications for patients' time and financial situation. Schneider et al. [13] state that in Austria, family members often bear the costs associated with private wound management clinics. In an Australian study, Kapp et al. [12] demonstrated that participation in the workforce is often challenging for those affected, as they rely on professional care and have to be available at home or attend appointments for care. Working in paid employment was also described as difficult due to pain, the challenge of finding work that does not aggravate the wound, and due to encountering barriers when seeking employment while, e.g. wearing orthopaedic footwear [12].

Chronic wounds pose a notable challenge for patients, healthcare professionals, and the healthcare systems [14, 15]. They have also been referred to as a 'silent pandemic' [16, 17]. Internationally, a prevalence of 2.21 per 1,000 population is assumed, which is expected to increase steadily in the coming years due to demographic changes and consequently higher numbers of comorbidities in older age [18]. Thus, managing chronic wounds has a significant impact on the healthcare system's economy [16, 17]. Amputations related to diabetes resulted in the highest costs, mainly due to prolonged hospital stays and subsequent expenses, including rehabilitation and outpatient care treatments [11].

Medical support is often sought only when the patient or their relatives feel overwhelmed by the wound. However, consulting a healthcare professional earlier in the course of the disease would likely improve healthcare outcomes or even prevent the development of the wound altogether [13]. Consequently, early diagnosis and preventive interventions tailored to the patient's needs are imperative [19, 20].

Patients with chronic wounds experience health disparities in various ways that reflect their diverse care requirements, highlighting the need for analysis from an intersectional perspective [21, 22]. Numerous studies have examined the burden of chronic wounds through multiple determinants, including age, sex, and comorbidities [23-27]. Despite the existing literature on biological and environmental factors influencing wound healing, there remains a gap in addressing sex disparities and sociocultural gender differences in healthcare utilisation and the comorbidity burden of patients with chronic wounds. A significant knowledge gap persists in systematically disaggregating clinical data by sex and incorporating gender-based perspectives into health planning for chronic wound care. To bridge this gap, this study analyses chronic wound care from the perspective of sex and gender as determinants of wound health. Data from

electronic health records (EHRs) of chronic wound patients are linked to the records of the Austrian Health Insurance Fund to gain insights into sex- and gender-based healthcare utilisation patterns, underlying aetiologies with a detailed analysis of atypical wounds, comorbidities, and the financial circumstances of patients with chronic wounds. Furthermore, the integration of these determinants into healthcare planning and interventions for individuals with chronic wounds will be discussed to inform policymakers, care providers, and researchers.

Methods

Study design and population

We conducted a retrospective observational cohort study using pseudonymised EHRs derived from an outpatient wound clinic in Vienna. The study population consisted of patients who received treatment for chronic wounds of various aetiologies at the outpatient wound clinic. The wound centre is a specialised outpatient clinic for the treatment of chronic wounds in the Vienna metropolitan area, funded by statutory health insurance. The outpatient clinic has been awarded the ICW Wound Seal® by the Initiative for Chronic Wounds (ICW), a quality seal for specialised healthcare facilities treating chronic wounds.

Austria is recognised as a welfare state, characterised by its statutory social insurance programmes that include mandatory pension, health insurance, and a work accident insurance scheme. These components constitute the most significant elements of the Austrian social security system [28]. One form of additional financial assistance available is the exemption from prescription fees. Individuals whose cumulative prescription fees exceed 2% of their annual net income are exempt from additional prescription charges [29]. An additional text file offers further details [see Additional file 1]. We therefore included the exemption from

prescription charges in our analysis as an indicator of financial vulnerability, since people with low income are particularly entitled to this exemption [30].

Eligibility criteria for the study required participants to be at least 18 years old.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics were calculated. Absolute and relative frequencies, along with percentages, were presented for categorical variables, and means and standard deviations were calculated for continuous variables. Patient characteristics were compared by sex and age group using the chi-squared test. 95% confidence intervals were calculated using the Clopper–Pearson method. It was determined that no correction for multiple testing would be applied, as this analysis is exploratory.

As clinical data were recorded in free text fields, we utilised natural language processing techniques to extract relevant information. An additional document provides further details regarding the NLP methodology and its implementation [see Additional file 2]. A supplementary table lists all keywords identified through EHR tokenisation [see Additional file 3]. A researcher also classified the free text fields of 200 patients (5.2%) regarding the presence of specific diagnoses and thus assessed whether the algorithm worked.

Patients were divided into six wound aetiology groups: arteriovenous ulcer, chronic peripheral venous insufficiency of lower extremities, diabetic foot syndrome, chronic arterial occlusive disease, pressure ulcer and/or atypical wounds. The aetiological nosology of the diagnoses is presented in accordance with the International Classification of Diseases, 11th Revision (ICD-11), where applicable; otherwise, it is supported by references to relevant literature.

Comorbidities were systematically classified using the main chapters of the ICD-11. An additional table provides further details [see Additional file 4]. To verify the accuracy of the statistical methods employed for analysing the frequencies of patient visits and sex differences, we conducted a sensitivity analysis.

The analyses were conducted using R (www.r-project.org).

Results

The study period spanned from 23 October 2019 to 6 December 2023. The study included medical records of 5,137 patients from the outpatient wound clinic. Patients without diagnostic information (n = 33) and those not undergoing treatment (n = 384) were excluded. We also excluded patients under the age of 18 (n = 177) and those without chronic wounds (n = 696). Finally, 3,847 patients with a total of 144,643 recorded visits were included in the analysis. An additional file provides a detailed explanation of exclusion criteria and includes the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) flow chart [see Additional file 5]. Furthermore, the completed STROBE statement checklist is included as supplementary material [see Additional file 6].

For a subset of 2,912 patients insured with the Austrian Health Insurance Fund, data on prescription fee status was available from 1 January 2018 to 30 September 2023.

We used the physician-reported biological sex, which is limited to the two categories of female and male. Sex was almost evenly distributed (47.8% female). Participant age was standardised by calculating their age based on their date of birth and first clinic visit. The mean age was 68.3 years (± 16.4 , median 72).

Figure 1. Age group distribution

As seen in Figure 1, the age groups were defined in five-year intervals, commencing with an initial group of ≤ 20 years. Since individuals under 18 years were excluded, this leads to a truncated entry group. All subsequent 16 groups covered a five-year interval, with an open upper limit for individuals aged >100 years. Within the age range of 18 to 30 years (62 versus 58) and above 80 years, the female population exceeded the male population (565 versus 382). Conversely, in the age range of 46 to 80 years, males were predominant. With both sexes taken together, the demographic cohort aged 76 to 80 constituted the largest population.

Table 1. Sample Characteristics. Significant differences are marked in red.

Characteristics	All (n = 3847) n (%), 95% CI	Female (n = 1840) n (%), 95% CI	Male (n = 2007) n (%), 95% CI	p-value
Age in years (Md, IQR)	72 [58 to 80]	74 [60 to 82]	69 [58 to 79]	<0.001
Age in years (M, \pm SD)	68.25 (\pm 16.40)	70.03 (\pm 17.04)	66.62 (\pm 15.61)	<0.001

Aetiology of chronic wound

Arteriovenous ulcer	202 (5.3, 4.6-6.0)	97 (5.3, 4.3-6.4)	105 (5.2, 4.3-6.3)	1.000
CVI*	496 (12.9, 11.8-14.0)	284 (15.4, 13.8-17.2)	212 (10.6, 9.3-12.0)	<0.001
Diabetic foot syndrome	683 (17.8, 16.6-19.0)	271 (14.7, 13.1-16.4)	412 (20.5, 18.8-22.4)	<0.001
Chronic arterial occlusive disease without CVI	766 (19.9, 18.7-21.2)	265 (14.4, 12.8-16.1)	501 (25.0, 23.1-26.9)	<0.001
Pressure ulcer	469 (12.2, 11.2-13.3)	219 (11.9, 10.5-13.5)	250 (12.5, 11.0-14.0)	0.634
Atypical wounds	187 (4.9, 4.2-5.6)	73 (4.0, 3.1-5.0)	114 (5.7, 4.7-6.8)	0.017

Comorbidities according to ICD-11

Certain infectious or parasitic diseases	325 (8.4, 7.6-9.4)	135 (7.3, 6.2-8.6)	190 (9.5, 8.2-10.8)	0.021
Neoplasms	335 (8.7, 7.8-9.6)	156 (8.5, 7.2-9.8)	179 (8.9, 7.7-10.3)	0.669
Endocrine, nutritional or metabolic diseases	1893 (49.2, 47.6-50.8)	808 (43.9, 41.6-46.2)	1085 (54.1, 51.9-56.3)	<0.001
MBND**	138 (3.6, 3.0-4.2)	58 (3.2, 2.4-4.1)	80 (4.0, 3.2-4.9)	0.193
Diseases of the circulatory system	1119 (29.1, 27.7-30.6)	472 (25.7, 23.7-27.7)	647 (32.2, 30.2-34.3)	<0.001
Diseases of the musculo-skeletal system***	267 (6.9, 6.2-7.9)	100 (5.4, 4.4-6.6)	167 (8.3, 7.1-9.6)	0.001
Diseases of the genitourinary system	255 (6.6, 5.9-7.5)	104 (5.7, 4.6-6.8)	151 (7.5, 6.4-8.8)	0.023

Injuries, symptoms, signs or clinical findings

...Delayed healing of surgical wound of skin	400 (10.4, 9.5-11.4)	175 (9.5, 8.2-10.9)	225 (11.2, 9.9-12.7)	0.094
Diabetes mellitus	1844 (47.9, 46.3-49.5)	781 (42.4, 40.1-44.7)	1063 (53.0, 50.8-55.2)	<0.001
Gangrene	221 (5.7, 5.0-6.5)	63 (3.4, 2.6-4.4)	158 (7.9, 6.7-9.1)	<0.001
Multidrug-resistant pathogen	457 (11.9, 10.9-12.9)	191 (10.4, 9.0-11.9)	266 (13.3, 11.8-14.8)	0.007
Necrosis	1126 (29.3, 27.8-30.7)	463 (25.2, 23.1-27.2)	663 (33.0, 31.0-35.1)	<0.001
Oedema	877 (22.8, 21.5-24.2)	396 (21.5, 19.7-23.5)	481 (24.0, 22.1-25.9)	0.077
Polyneuropathy	964 (25.1, 23.7-26.5)	361 (19.6, 17.8-21.5)	603 (30.0, 28.0-32.1)	<0.001
Posttraumatic impaired wound healing	1143 (29.7, 28.3-31.2)	513 (27.9, 25.8-30.0)	630 (31.4, 29.4-33.5)	0.019

Factors influencing health status

Amputation	512 (13.3, 12.3-14.4)	151 (8.2, 7.0-9.6)	361 (18.0, 16.3-19.7)	<0.001
Dependence on wheelchair	124 (3.2, 2.7-3.8)	36 (2.0, 1.4-2.7)	88 (4.4, 3.5-5.4)	<0.001

* Chronic peripheral venous insufficiency of lower extremities without chronic arterial occlusive disease, ** Mental, behavioural or neurodevelopmental disorders, *** or connective tissue

As seen in Table 1, the most common causes of chronic wounds were chronic arterial occlusive disease (PAD) without chronic peripheral venous insufficiency of lower extremities (CVI) in 766 patients (19.9%) followed by diabetic foot syndrome (DFS) in 683 patients (17.8%) and CVI in 496 patients (12.9%). If patients had a PAD and CVI diagnosis, these were assigned to the aetiology of arteriovenous ulcers instead of PAD and CVI. A total of 202 patients (5.3%) have been diagnosed with arteriovenous ulcers. Patients with skin ulcers, diabetes mellitus,

polyneuropathy, and/or chronic arterial occlusive disease were also classified under DFS. Significant sex-specific differences were observed in PAD, DFS, and CVI ($p < 0.001$). CVI was more common in females (15.4% in females versus 10.6% in males), whereas PAD (25% in males and 14.4% in females) and DFS (20.5% in males and 14.7% in females) were notably more prevalent in males. Figure 2 displays the relative frequencies of chronic wound diagnoses, stratified by sex.

Figure 2. Relative frequencies of chronic wound diagnoses stratified by sex.

Of the 3,847 patients, 1,893 patients (49.2%) had comorbidities classified within endocrine, nutritional, and metabolic diseases, followed by diseases of the circulatory system in 1,119 patients (29.1%). Although there was an almost equal sex distribution, men had a higher prevalence of multiple comorbidities and symptomatic or clinical findings, with significant values ($p < 0.001$) also observed for diabetes mellitus, gangrene, necrosis, polyneuropathy, and dependence on a wheelchair. When comparing the relative frequencies of the various

characteristics, polyneuropathy (30% in males and 19.6% in females) and amputations (18% in males and 8.2% in females) were the most divergent. When comparing the absolute frequencies of amputations, there was more than a twofold difference between the sexes (361 versus 151). The additional sensitivity analysis revealed that a similar distribution could also be observed in patients over 70 years [see Additional file 7]. Within this subpopulation, compared to the entire study population, no significant sex differences were found concerning diabetic foot syndrome ($p = .001$), necrosis ($p = .002$) and dependence on a wheelchair ($p = .022$).

In this study, atypical wounds were categorised into malignant tumours, inflammatory processes, and alcohol and substance use disorders (ASUD). Malignant wounds included basal cell carcinoma (BCC), malignant melanoma (melanoma), and squamous cell carcinoma (SCC). Inflammatory processes included pyoderma gangrenosum (pyoderma), hidradenitis suppurativa (hidradenitis), panniculitis, and vasculitis. Out of the 187 atypical wounds, 73 were assigned to women and 114 to men.

Figure 3. Relative frequencies of underlying conditions associated with atypical wounds.

As demonstrated in Figure 3, the atypical wounds in more than half of patients are caused by neoplastic factors, with ASUD being the next most common. Among men, the prevalence of ASUD was almost three times higher compared to women (34.1% in males and 12.5% in females).

Figure 4. Stacked bar chart showing the relative frequencies of patient visits in the outpatient wound clinic by age group and sex.

Figure 4 displays the treatment intensity. To analyse the distribution of visits among different age groups and between sexes, the number of visits was categorised into five predefined intervals of 25 visits each, and a category for more than 100 visits. These visit groups were combined with age groups and stratified by sex. An additional file provides the numerical breakdown of these findings [see Additional file 8]. The highest treatment intensity,

characterised by over 100 visits, occurs more frequently among men across various age groups, whereas it is less prevalent and less concentrated among women. Among male patients, the proportion receiving the maximum treatment intensity steadily increases, reaching its peak within the 56-60 age cohort. Conversely, female patients reach this peak in the 76-80 age group. In age groups under 41 years, outpatient treatments are generally infrequent and predominantly limited to lower-intensity categories for both sexes. Sensitivity analysis confirmed the robustness of these findings [see Additional file 9]. Males exhibit a higher frequency of visits and prolonged treatment durations for chronic wounds at the outpatient clinic.

Figure 5. Duration of treatment in months, categorised by diagnoses and sex

Figure 5 illustrates the duration of treatment in months for patients with CVI, DFS, PAD, posttraumatic impaired wound healing, and pressure ulcer, disaggregated by sex.

Table 2. Distribution of prescription fee exemptions

Prescription Fee Status	All (n = 2912)	Female (n = 1471)	Male (n = 1441)
Exempt	2084 (71.6)	1063 (36.5)	1021 (35.1)
Not Exempt	828 (28.4)	408 (14.0)	420 (14.4)

Table 2 presents the prescription fee exemption for patients insured with the Austrian Health Insurance Fund. Patients were classified as exempt from the prescription fee based on having one documented record of exemption during the observation period. Over two-thirds of this subpopulation qualified for exemption from prescription charges. Women had a slightly higher rate of prescription fee exemptions at 36.5% compared to 35.1% for men.

Discussion

The findings indicate that, despite an almost equal distribution by sex, men showed a significantly higher prevalence of DFS, PAD, endocrine, nutritional or metabolic disorders, diseases of the circulatory system, gangrene, necrosis, and polyneuropathy. Men experienced more amputations and were more often reliant on wheelchairs. Conversely, women were diagnosed with these conditions less frequently, despite their comparable representation within the study population. Furthermore, men visited the wound centre at a markedly higher rate than women, even at a younger age.

The underlying causes of chronic wound aetiology differ across various studies. In our study, PAD was the most common cause, accounting for nearly one-fifth of the cases. Körber et al. [5] found in their expert survey, and Mekkes et al. [6], in their topical review, that the predominant aetiological factors of leg ulcers are venous, arterial, or arteriovenous. This only partially aligns with the data from our study. After PAD, the most common underlying aetiology

is diabetic foot syndrome, followed by CVI. Compared to the survey by Körber et al. [5], which found CVI as the main cause in nearly half of the patients and arteriovenous ulcers in almost 18%, CVI and arteriovenous ulcers are relatively rare in our study, occurring in 12.9% and 5.3% of patients. Interestingly, a similar distribution of the aetiology of chronic wounds was recorded in the single-centre study by Wolny et al. [31], with the predominant causes being diabetes (30.9%) and post-traumatic wounds (25.5%), followed by pressure ulcers (14.8%), surgical site infections (14.8%), and vascular ulcers (14.1%). In our study, post-traumatic wounds affected 29.7% of patients. One explanation for this might be that the study by Wolny et al. [31] included patients from a surgical outpatient clinic. Since a surgeon also leads the wound centre, this is a key factor in understanding its specialisation in treating post-traumatic wounds and those with delayed healing of surgical skin wounds. One reason for the high proportion of diabetes patients could be that one of the co-founders of the wound centre was the president of the umbrella organisation for Austrian diabetes self-help groups.

In this study, we aimed to elucidate the underlying causes of atypical wounds. As Isoherranen et al. and Janowska et al. [8, 33] found, approximately 20% of chronic wounds are atypical, and most remain undiagnosed. This might also explain why atypical wounds account for only around 4.9% in our study. Furthermore, chronic wounds are a particularly sensitive issue, especially for those with non-healing wounds resulting from alcohol and substance use disorders. It stands to reason that the number of unreported cases in this field is considerably greater, as patients often avoid seeking healthcare due to limited access, stigma, or lack of patient readiness [32].

The most common comorbidities identified in our study align with those reported by Kuikko et al. [24], which also include endocrine, nutritional, or metabolic diseases. The authors highlight hypertension as another prevalent comorbidity [24]. Following endocrine, nutritional, or

metabolic diseases, the most common comorbidities in our study were diseases of the circulatory system and neoplasms, which ranked third.

Regarding sex differences, a single-centre study by Kuikko et al. [25] found that diabetic foot ulcers and pressure ulcers are more common in males. Conversely, arteriovenous ulcers and CVI occur more frequently in women [24], which aligns with our study's findings. In contrast to Kuikko et al.'s research [24], PAD and atypical wounds were more prevalent in men in our study. According to Dao [27], being male is considered a risk factor for abnormal healing in older age, as men demonstrate an altered inflammatory response and take longer than women to heal acute wounds. Another aspect contributing to the higher prevalence of comorbidities and more frequent visits to the outpatient wound clinic at an earlier age is that men seek health services too late [33, 34]. This is also reflected in the significantly higher number of amputations. This aligns with findings from previous studies stating that men had a higher risk of undergoing amputations [35-37].

Prescription fee exemption allows only an estimation of low income. Being at risk of poverty is accompanied by significant social or material deprivation [39]. In 2022, 2.3% of the total Austrian population lived in poverty and social exclusion [40]. Empirical findings indicate that socioeconomic status and environmental factors hinder wound healing by increasing pain response, influencing hormonal and inflammatory responses, and increasing the risk of infection [20].

Relying on data from a single outpatient clinic limits the generalisation of our findings. Furthermore, the retrospective design prevents drawing any causal inferences. Our study analysed comorbidities, aware that the concept of comorbidity lacks consensus [38]. At the same time, this categorisation is essential from the perspective of effectively implementing

health promotion strategies tailored to the needs of patients and improving healthcare outcomes for patients with chronic wounds.

Conclusion

This is the first empirical study characterising chronic wound patients in Austria. Understanding the various patient health and healthcare trajectories broken down by sex is crucial for patient-centred interventions and improving healthcare outcomes. Although a substantial scholarship currently exists surrounding sex-informed research, its systematic integration into clinical care remains outstanding [41].

Individuals suffering from chronic diseases face a higher risk of psychological distress compared to those who are physically healthy [42]. This observation is especially significant for individuals with chronic wounds, who often belong to the elderly demographic and present multiple comorbid conditions. Psychological stress, along with negative emotions like anxiety and depression, impacts health, immune regulation, and wound healing, ultimately leading to increased patient morbidity [42]. This study indicates that individuals seeking treatment at the outpatient clinic for wound care predominantly come from lower socioeconomic backgrounds. Chronic wounds serve as a clear example of the importance of addressing social determinants of health. Therefore, poverty reduction is a key measure aimed at improving people's living and working conditions [43]. Gender-based determinants, such as income and social roles, may also contribute to pathways influencing health outcomes [44]. Marczak et al. [45] emphasise the importance of establishing new routines in primary health care and social services to educate patients on when to seek treatment and to identify individuals with leg ulcers earlier in their illness. Particular attention should be paid, especially, to the early preventive care of men's health and to delivering timely, accessible wound care to low-income populations through a

multidisciplinary team approach. Furthermore, health promotion needs to be integrated into regular wound care.

List of abbreviations

ASUD	Alcohol and substance use disorders
BCC	Basal cell carcinoma
CI	Confidence interval
CVI	Chronic peripheral venous insufficiency of lower extremities
DFS	Diabetic foot syndrome
EHR	Electronic health record
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICD-11	International Classification of Diseases, 11th Revision
ICW	Initiative for Chronic Wounds (Initiative Chronische Wunden e.V., Germany)
NLP	Natural language processing
PAD	Chronic peripheral arterial occlusive disease
SCC	Squamous cell carcinoma
STROBE	Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Lars Grespan for his computational support at the early stages of the project, and to Mark Mussner for both his technical assistance and contributions to refining the research focus. We also thank Preston Long and Nadja Kartschmit for their methodological advice. Finally, we are grateful to Michael Vorstandlechner for proofreading the manuscript.

Author contributions

K.M, R.H. and T.S. conceptualised the study. K.M, R.H., A.P., V.R., C.S., S.W. and T.S. curated, analysed and interpreted the data. All authors drafted and approved the manuscript.

Funding

The Ludwig Boltzmann Research Group Senescence and Healing of Wounds was supported by Nationalstiftung für Forschung, Technologie und Entwicklung (grant NFTE 2019–6) and Allgemeine Unfallversicherungsanstalt (AUVA). The funders were not involved in any process of this research.

Availability of data and materials

The data utilised in this study are obtained from EHRs and encompass sensitive patient information. In accordance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), this data is not publicly available.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

The Ethics Committee of the Medical University of Vienna approved this study in July 2023 (EK Nr: 1464/2023). Due to the retrospective nature of the study, informed consent could not be obtained from the patients. The data is pseudonymised, and both data storage and processing comply with Austrian data protection laws and GDPR.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Competing interests

R.H. acquired the funding for this study and is a consultant for the city of Vienna on chronic wound care policy. K.M is the founder of a self-help group for patients with chronic wounds in Vienna. A.P. is vice president of the Austrian Wound Association and has given lectures on chronic wound care in professional settings. The institution affiliated with A.P. received compensation for these lectures. A.P. provided access to the data used in this study. C.S. has given a lecture on chronic wound care and received an expense allowance. R.H., K.M., A.P. and C.S. declare that these professional engagements did not influence the design, analysis, or interpretation of the study results. T.S. reports personal fees from AbbVie, Roche, Sanofi, Takeda, and Novartis, outside the submitted work. V.R. and S.W. declare no competing interests.

References

1. Falanga, V., R.R. Isseroff, A.M. Soulika, M. Romanelli, D. Margolis, S. Kapp, M. Granick, and K. Harding, *Chronic wounds*. Nature Reviews Disease Primers, 2022. **8**(1).
2. Lazarus, G.S., D.M. Cooper, D.R. Knighton, D.J. Margolis, R.E. Percoraro, G. Rodeheaver, and M.C. Robson, *Definitions and guidelines for assessment of wounds and evaluation of healing*. Wound repair and regeneration, 1994. **2**(3): p. 165-170.
3. Kyaw, B.M., K. Järbrink, L. Martinengo, J. Car, K. Harding, and A. Schmidtchen, *Need for Improved Definition of "Chronic Wounds" in Clinical Studies*. Acta Derm Venereol, 2018. **98**(1): p. 157-158.
4. Jarbrink, K., G. Ni, H. Sonnergren, A. Schmidtchen, C. Pang, R. Bajpai, and J. Car, *Prevalence and incidence of chronic wounds and related complications: a protocol for a systematic review*. Syst Rev, 2016. **5**(1): p. 152.
5. Körber, A., J. Klode, S. Al-Benna, C. Wax, D. Schadendorf, L. Steinstraesser, and J. Dissemond, *Etiology of chronic leg ulcers in 31,619 patients in Germany analyzed by an expert survey*. J Dtsch Dermatol Ges, 2011. **9**(2): p. 116-21.

6. Mekkes, J.R., M.A. Loots, A.C. Van Der Wal, and J.D. Bos, *Causes, investigation and treatment of leg ulceration*. Br J Dermatol, 2003. **148**(3): p. 388-401.
7. Becker, S.L., S. Kody, N.M. Fett, A. Hines, A. Alavi, and A.G. Ortega-Loayza, *Approach to the Atypical Wound*. American Journal of Clinical Dermatology, 2024. **25**(4): p. 559-584.
8. Janowska, A., V. Dini, T. Oranges, M. Iannone, B. Loggini, and M. Romanelli, *Atypical Ulcers: Diagnosis and Management*. Clin Interv Aging, 2019. **14**: p. 2137-2143.
9. Hoffman, M.D., *Atypical ulcers*. Dermatol Ther, 2013. **26**(3): p. 222-35.
10. Shelling, M.L., D.G. Federman, and R.S. Kirsner, *Clinical approach to atypical wounds with a new model for understanding hypertensive ulcers*. Arch Dermatol, 2010. **146**(9): p. 1026-9.
11. Olsson, M., K. Jarbrink, U. Divakar, R. Bajpai, Z. Upton, A. Schmidtchen, and J. Car, *The humanistic and economic burden of chronic wounds: A systematic review*. Wound Repair and Regeneration, 2019. **27**: p. 114-125.
12. Kapp, S., C. Miller, and N. Santamaria, *The quality of life of people who have chronic wounds and who self-treat*. Journal of Clinical Nursing, 2018. **27**(1-2): p. 182-192.
13. Schneider, C., D. Drgac, M. Niederleithinger, V. Hruschka, and R. Himmelsbach, *Die Versorgung chronischer Wunden durch das österreichische Gesundheitssystem - eine Übersicht*. 2022.
14. Jain, K., P. Avsar, D. Patton, Z. Moore, and B. Murray, *What specific challenges do patients with chronic wounds encounter when attending medical appointments related to wound care? A systematic review*. Journal of Tissue Viability, 2025. **34**(2): p. 100865.
15. Frykberg, R.G. and J. Banks, *Challenges in the Treatment of Chronic Wounds*. Adv Wound Care (New Rochelle), 2015. **4**(9): p. 560-582.
16. Graves, N., C.J. Phillips, and K. Harding, *A narrative review of the epidemiology and economics of chronic wounds*. Br J Dermatol, 2022. **187**(2): p. 141-148.
17. Sen, C.K., G.M. Gordillo, S. Roy, R. Kirsner, L. Lambert, T.K. Hunt, F. Gottrup, G.C. Gurtner, and M.T. Longaker, *Human skin wounds: a major and snowballing threat to public health and the economy*. Wound Repair Regen, 2009. **17**(6): p. 763-71.
18. Martinengo, L., M. Olsson, R. Bajpai, M. Soljak, Z. Upton, A. Schmidtchen, J. Car, and K. Järbrink, *Prevalence of chronic wounds in the general population: systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies*, in *Annals of Epidemiology*. 2019, Elsevier Inc. p. 8-15.

19. Ahmajärvi, K.M., K.M. Isoherranen, T.J. Pessi, and M.A. Venermo, *The Impact of Diagnostic Delay on Wound Healing-A Cohort Study in a Primary Care Setting*. *Int Wound J*, 2025. **22**(5): p. e70141.
20. Sen, C.K., *Human Wound and Its Burden: Updated 2022 Compendium of Estimates*. *Adv Wound Care (New Rochelle)*, 2023. **12**(12): p. 657-670.
21. Alvarez-Irusta, L., T. Van Durme, A.S. Lambert, and J. Macq, *People with chronic wounds cared for at home in Belgium: Prevalence and exploration of care integration needs using health care trajectory analysis*. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 2022. **135**.
22. Almeida, J., J. Brocklehurst, and A. Sharples, *Intersectionality, vulnerability and foot health inequity*. *J Foot Ankle Res*, 2023. **16**(1): p. 73.
23. Jockenhöfer, F., H. Gollnick, K. Herberger, G. Isbary, R. Renner, M. Stücker, E. Valesky, U. Wollina, M. Weichenthal, S. Karrer, B. Kuepper, A. Roesch, and J. Dissemmond, *Aetiology, comorbidities and cofactors of chronic leg ulcers: retrospective evaluation of 1 000 patients from 10 specialised dermatological wound care centers in Germany*. *Int Wound J*, 2016. **13**(5): p. 821-8.
24. Kuikko, K., T. Salmi, H. Huhtala, and T. Kimpimäki, *Characteristics of chronic ulcer patients by gender and ulcer aetiology from a multidisciplinary wound centre*. *Int Wound J*, 2024. **21**(8): p. e70012.
25. Morrison, A. and A.W. Aday, *Sex as a key determinant of peripheral artery disease: epidemiology, differential outcomes, and proposed biological mechanisms*. *Canadian Journal of Cardiology*, 2022. **38**(5): p. 601-611.
26. Ciarambino, T., P. Crispino, G. Leto, E. Mastrolorenzo, O. Para, and M. Giordano, *Influence of Gender in Diabetes Mellitus and Its Complication*. *Int J Mol Sci*, 2022. **23**(16).
27. Dao, H. and R.A. Kazin, *Gender differences in skin: A review of the literature*. *Gender Medicine*, 2007. **4**(4): p. 308-328.
28. *Federal Ministry Labour, Social Affairs, Health, Care and Consumer Protection. Republic of Austria*. Available from: <https://www.sozialministerium.at/en/Topics/Social-Affairs/Social-Insurance.html>. Accessed on 2 April 2025.
29. *Österreichische Gesundheitskasse. Rezepte und Rezeptgebührenbefreiung 2025*. Available from: <https://www.gesundheitskasse.at/cdscontent/?contentid=10007.870471&portal=oegkportal>. Accessed on 25 March 2025.

30. Czypionka, T., G. Röhrling, and E. Six, *Can people afford to pay for health care? New evidence on financial protection in Austria*. 2018.
31. Wolny, D., L. Štěpánek, D. Horáková, J. Thomas, J. Zapletalová, and M.S. Patel, *Risk Factors for Non-Healing Wounds-A Single-Centre Study*. J Clin Med, 2024. **13**(4).
32. Vogel, E.A., K. Ly, D.E. Ramo, and J. Satterfield, *Strategies to improve treatment utilization for substance use disorders: A systematic review of intervention studies*. Drug and Alcohol Dependence, 2020. **212**: p. 108065.
33. Galdas, P.M., F. Cheater, and P. Marshall, *Men and health help-seeking behaviour: literature review*. J Adv Nurs, 2005. **49**(6): p. 616-23.
34. Thompson, A.E., Y. Anisimowicz, B. Miedema, W. Hogg, W.P. Wodchis, and K. Aubrey-Bassler, *The influence of gender and other patient characteristics on health care-seeking behaviour: a QUALICOPC study*. BMC Fam Pract, 2016. **17**: p. 38.
35. López-de-Andrés, A., M.A. Martínez-Huedo, P. Carrasco-Garrido, V. Hernández-Barrera, A. Gil-de-Miguel, and R. Jiménez-García, *Trends in lower-extremity amputations in people with and without diabetes in Spain, 2001-2008*. Diabetes Care, 2011. **34**(7): p. 1570-6.
36. Amin, L., B.R. Shah, A.S. Bierman, L.L. Lipscombe, C.F. Wu, D.S. Feig, and G.L. Booth, *Gender differences in the impact of poverty on health: disparities in risk of diabetes-related amputation*. Diabetic Medicine, 2014. **31**(11): p. 1410-1417.
37. McGinagle, K.L., G. Doros, O. Alabi, B.S. Brooke, A. Vouyouka, J. Hiramoto, K. Charlton-Ouw, M.B. Strong, K. Rosenfield, M.T. Menard, A. Farber, and K.A. Giles, *Female patients have fewer limb amputations compared to male patients in the BEST-CLI trial*. J Vasc Surg, 2025. **81**(2): p. 366-373.e1.
38. Valderas, J.M., B. Starfield, B. Sibbald, C. Salisbury, and M. Roland, *Defining comorbidity: implications for understanding health and health services*. Ann Fam Med, 2009. **7**(4): p. 357-63.
39. *Statistics Austria - Poverty and Social Inclusion*. Available from: https://www.statistik.at/fileadmin/pages/338/FAQs_zum_Thema_Armut_und_soziale_Eingliederung.pdf. Accessed on 6 May 2025.
40. *Poverty Watch Report - Austria 2023*. 2024; Available from: <https://www.eapn.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/eapn-EAPN-AT-English-version-2023-PW-5900.pdf>. Accessed on 6 May 2025.
41. Bartz, D., T. Chitnis, U.B. Kaiser, J.W. Rich-Edwards, K.M. Rexrode, P.B. Pennell, J.M. Goldstein, M.A. O'Neal, M. LeBoff, M. Behn, E.W. Seely, H. Joffe, and J.E.

- Manson, *Clinical Advances in Sex- and Gender-Informed Medicine to Improve the Health of All: A Review*. JAMA Internal Medicine, 2020. **180**(4): p. 574-583.
42. Basu, S., A.G. Goswami, L.E. David, and E. Mudge, *Psychological stress on wound healing: a silent player in a complex background*. The International Journal of Lower Extremity Wounds, 2024. **23**(3): p. 365-371.
43. Marmot, M., *The health gap: the challenge of an unequal world*. The Lancet, 2015. **386**(10011): p. 2442-2444.
44. Courtenay, W.H., *Constructions of masculinity and their influence on men's well-being: a theory of gender and health*. Social Science & Medicine, 2000. **50**(10): p. 1385-1401.
45. Marczak, J., G. Rembeck, E.L. Petersson, and L. Nordeman, *Patient experiences of living with chronic leg ulcers and making the decision to seek professional health-care*. J Wound Care, 2019. **28**(Sup1): p. S18-s25.

Additional Files

Additional file 1. Prescription fees and exemption from prescription fees in Austria

The prescription fee cap became effective in 2008 [1]. According to § 31 (5) no. 16 of the General Social Insurance Act, individuals whose cumulative prescription fees exceed 2% of their annual net income are exempt from additional prescription charges [1]. Furthermore, individuals are exempt from the prescription fee if they pay a minimum of 41 prescription charges within a calendar year.

In 2023, the prescription fee in Austria was set at €6.85 for each prescription [2]. 12% of the population in Vienna covered by the Austrian Health Insurance Fund (corresponding to approximately 1.8 million people) were exempt from prescription fees this year. We calculated this using monthly mean values of the total number of individuals who received a prescription fee exemption over a one-year period. Patients privately pay for medications that cost less than this amount, resulting in these transactions not being recorded in the billing records of the Austrian Health Insurance Fund. Certain individuals are exempt from prescription fees due to various circumstances. The following groups of people are automatically exempt from the prescription fee: Recipients of a compensatory allowance, civil servants, those receiving social assistance covered by health insurance, asylum seekers, self-insured individuals caring for a disabled child, participants in voluntary social or environmental programs, persons treated for notifiable communicable diseases, and individuals covered by the War Victims' Benefits Act, Army Benefits Act, or Victims' Welfare Act. In cases where these exempt individuals obtain medication subject to the prescription fee, they can seek reimbursement from the health insurance fund, leading to its inclusion in the database [3].

References

1. *Gesundheit*, in *Handbuch Armut in Österreich*, N. Dimmel, S. Martin, and C. Stelzer-Orthofer, Editors. 2014, Studienverlag: Innsbruck.
2. *Leistungsrechtliche Werte in der Sozialversicherung 2023*. Available from: <https://www.sozialversicherung.at/cdscontent/load?contentid=10008.773699&version=1676364120>. Accessed on 8 May 2025.
3. *Österreichische Gesundheitskasse. Rezepte und Rezeptgebührenbefreiung 2025*. Available from: <https://www.gesundheitskasse.at/cdscontent/?contentid=10007.870471&portal=oegkportal>. Accessed on 25 March 2025.

Additional file 2. Natural Language Processing - methodology and implementation

Word tokenisation was employed to identify the underlying diagnosis of the chronic wound and the comorbidities. A semantic space was created through the process of stemming the words, with the removal of stop words (e.g., 'and', 'the', 'a', and similar words), and the conversion of all text to lowercase. Furthermore, punctuation marks, names, and personal words were excluded from the text. Following word tokenisation, the individual tokens were exported to Excel. In the next step, each token was manually assigned to the corresponding diagnoses or diagnostic category. A supplementary table lists all keywords identified through EHR tokenisation [see Additional file 3]. An algorithm was employed to search for keywords within the EHRs to ascertain the presence or absence of a diagnosis. During medical history taking, patients are routinely asked about their diabetes status. Consequently, entries such as “no Diabetes” are frequently encountered within the EHRs. Therefore, a “no” prior to a diabetes diagnosis resulted in the diagnosis not being recorded for this patient.

Additional file 3. Keywords identified through EHR tokenisation for diagnosis classification

Table 1. Keywords identified through EHR tokenisation with corresponding diagnoses

Diagnosis or diagnostic category	Keywords
Alcohol and substance use disorder	"Drogenabusus", "Drogen", "C2H5OH", "äthylisch", "abusus", "Abusus", "C2Abusus", "c2-abusus", "C2_abusus", "c2abusus", "C2Abusus", "c2-Abusus", "C2-Abusus", "toxische", "tox", "Substitutionsprogramm", "Substitoltherapie", "Substitolprogramm", "Substitol", "Polytoxikomanie", "Polytoxikomane", "Polytox", "nutriv", "nutritive", "nutritiv", "Nutr", "nutr", "alkoholische", "alkoholbedingtes", "alkohol", "Kokain", "Heroin"
Amputation	"Zehenanputation", "Zehenamputation", "ZEhenamp", "Zehenamp", "Z.n.Amputation", "Vorfußverschmälerung", "Vorfußamputation", "Vorfußamp", "teilverfußamp", "Teilamp", "Stumpfrevision", "Stumpfresektion", "Stumpf", "St.p.Amp", "st.p.Amp", "Post.amp", "Großzehenstrahlamputation", "Großzehenamp", "Grenzzonenamp", "Engliedamp", "Endphalanxamp", "amp", "Amp", "AMp", "AMP", "Amp.rechts", "Amp.stelle", "Amptatio", "Ampu", "Amputaionsstelle", "Amputatio", "amputation", "Amputation", "AMputation", "Amputationli", "Amputationsstelle", "Amputationsstumpf", "Amputationstumpf", "Amputatuin"
Anorectal conditions	"peranale", "Perineale", "perineal", "Perinale", "perinale", "Perianalvenenthrombose", "perianales", "perianaler", "perianalem", "Perianale", "perianale", "Perianalabszeß", "Perianal", "perianal", "peranale", "Marisken", "Mariske", "Hämorrhoid", "hämorrrh", "hämorrrhagica", "hämorrrhagicae", "Hämorrhoidalknoten", "Analfissur", "analfissur", "Nod. Häm.", "nod. häm.", "Nod. häm", "Analfibrom"
Animal-related injuries	"Zeckenstich", "Zeckenbiss", "Zecken", "Z.n.Insektenstich", "Schlangenbiss", "Katzenbiß", "Katzenbiss", "Katze", "Hund", "Hundebiss", "Hundebiß"
Arteriovenous ulcer	"mix", "mixta", "mixtum", "gemischt", "gemischte", "gemischtes"
Basal cell carcinoma	"Basacell", "Basalcell", "Basaliom", "Basaliome", "Basaliomen", "Basaliomexstirpation", "Basaliomrezidiv", "Basaliomrezidiv", "Basalzall", "Basalzell", "Basalzellcarcinom", "Basalzellkarzinomsund", "Bcc", "BCC"
Bursitis	"Bursitis"
Carbuncle	"Karbunkel"
Cardiovascular diseases	"VVI", "VVIR", "Kardiomyopathie", "Kammerflimmern", "Herklappen", "Herinsuff", "Flimrn", "FLimmern", "Flimmern", "flimmern", "Flimmer", "Flimmen", "FLi", "Fli", "DDD", "CRTD", "CRT", "Coronarangio", "Coronar", "coronar", "CorAngio", "Cor.angio", "biologischem", "Biolog", "biolog", "Bioherzklappe", "Bioaortenklappenersatz", "Z.n.ACBP", "VHfli", "VHF", "Trikuspidalklappenersatz", "Tricuspidalklappenersatz", "Tricuspidalinsuffizient", "TIA", "TAVI", "STEMI", "stemi", "Schrittmacherträgerin", "Schrittmacher", "Schlaganfall", "Rhythmusstörungen", "Rhythmusstörung", "Reinsult", "Rechtsherzinsuffizienz", "Rechtsherzdekompensation", "Perikarditis", "Perikarderguß", "Perikardektomie", "Paroxysmales", "paroxysmales", "paroxysm", "paroxysmales", "parox", "NYHA", "NSTEMI", "Myokardinfarkt", "Myokardinfarkt", "MYocardstent", "Myocarditis", "Myocardinfarkt", "Myocardinfarkt", "Mitrasklappeninsuffizienz", "Mitralvitium", "Mitralklappenrepair", "Mitralklappeninsuffizienz", "Mitralklappenersatz", "Mitral", "Mitra", "Mehretagenthrombose", "Koronarstent", "koronare", "Koronarbypass", "KHK", "ischämische", "ISchämie", "Ischämie", "iSchäm", "ischäm", "Insulte", "INSult", "Insult", "ICDT", "ICD", "Herz", "Herztransplantation", "Herzstillstand", "Herzschrittmacher", "Herzrhythmusstörungen", "Herzrhythmusstörung", "HerzOP", "Herzop", "HerzLungenMaschine", "HerzklappenOP", "Herzklappenersatz", "Herzklappen", "Herzklappe", "Herzkatheter", "Herzinsuffizienz", "Herzinsuffizie", "Herzinsuffiz", "Herzinsuff", "Herzbypass", "Endokarditis", "Endocarditis", "Endangiitis", "CVAK",

	"Coronarbypass", "Coronatstent", "Coronarunterventiomn", "Coronarstents", "Coronarstenting", "Coronarstent", "Coronarsent", "Coronarintervention", "Coronarbypass", "Coronarbypass", "Coronarbaypass", "Coronararterienstenose", "Coronabypass", "Cornarbypass", "3xACBP", "ACBP", "AOC", "AOCB", "AOCBP", "Anerurysma", "Aneursma", "Aneurysruptur", "Aneaurysma", "Aneurysma", "Aneurysmaauschaltung", "Aneurysmaresektion", "Aortenaneurysma", "Aortenaneurysma", "Aortendissektion", "Aortenektasie", "Aortenklappe", "Aortenklappenersatz", "Aortenklappensklerose", "Aortenklappenstenose", "Aortenstenose", "Aortenstent", "Aortenverschluss", "Aortocornarbypass", "Aortocoronarbypass", "Aortocoronarem", "Aortocoronaren", "aortokor", "Aortokoronarbypass", "Beckenvenenthrombose", "TVTs", "TVT", "Thrombose", "TBVT", "TBT"
Carpal tunnel syndrome	"CTS"
Chronic venous insufficiency	"PTS", "Spätthrombose", "Posttrombotisches", "posttromb", "postthromotisches", "Postthrombotisches", "postthrombotisches", "postthrombotischen", "postthromb", "postthrombh", "postthrombot", "Postthrombot", "Verödungstherapie", "Verödung", "Stripping", "venosum", "Venöses", "venöses", "venösen", "venosem", "Venöse", "venöse", "venosa", "Venös", "venös", "Venenverödung", "Venenverödung", "Venenstripping", "venenstripping", "VenenOPs", "VenenOP", "Venenop", "Veneninsuffizienz", "Varizenverödung", "Varizenstripping", "Varizenstripping", "Varizensklerosierung", "VArizenOP", "VarizenOP", "Varizennstripping", "Varizenkonvolut", "Varizenblutung", "Varizen", "Variten", "Varikostits", "VArikositas", "Varikositas", "Variköse", "Varikose", "Varikos", "Varicen", "Varicectomie", "Stammvarikositas", "Stammvarikos", "Stammvar", "Rezizivvarizen", "Rezidivvarikositas", "Leitveneninsuff", "CVI", "cvi", "Cvi", "Chronisch venöse Insuffizienz", "chronische venöse Insuffizienz", "chronisch venöse insuffizienz", "chron. Veneninsuffizienz"
Clavus	"Clavus"
Compartment syndrome	"KOmpartmentsyndrom", "Kompartment", "Faszienspaltung", "Compartment", "Compartmentssyndrom"
Condyloma acuminata	"Condylomentfernung", "Condylom", "Cond"
Cosmetic procedures	"Straffung", "Brustverkl.", "Reduktionsplastik", "Mammareduktionsplastik", "Mammaaugmentation", "Liposuktion", "Hautstraffung", "Facelifting", "Eigenfetttransplantation", "Bauchdeckenstraffung", "Bauchstraffung", "Bodylift", "Brustimpl", "Bruststraffung", "Brusttraffung", "Brustimplantat"
Delayed healing of surgical wound of skin	"Stumpfulkus", "Postamputationsulc", "Amp.Ulcus", "Amp.ulkus", "Amputationsstump", "Amputationsstumpfulcera", "Amputationsstumpfulkus", "Amputationsstumpulkus", "Amputationsulc", "Amputationsulcera", "Amputationsulcus", "amputationsulkus", "Amputationsulkus", "Amputationulcus", "St.p. ASK Li Knie", "zn Kreuzband-OP", "Venenentnahmestelle", "Venenentnahme", "Transplantentnahmestelle", "Tracheostomiewunde", "pstop", "Ps", "ps", "postp", "postoperatives", "postoperative", "postoperativ", "Postoper", "POstop", "Postop", "postOP", "postop", "Postinterventionelle", "postinterven", "postinterven", "Posptop", "p.Op", "p.OP", "WHS nach Ventrikelshuntrevision", "ST.p. Gleithernien OP", "Zn Halluex OP", "Amputationhswundee"
Diabetes mellitus	"Typ2", "tblpfl", "tbl", "tablpfl", "tablettentpfl", "tabl", "Retinopathie", "Retinpath", "Retinopathie", "retinopathie", "Praediabetes", "Prädiabetes", "NIDMM", "NIDMII", "NIDDMII", "NIDDMI", "NIDDM2", "NIDDM", "NIDDM", "NIDD", "MIDDM", "Mellitus", "mellitus", "Mell", "mell", "mel", "Makroangiopathie", "Ievis", "Ketoacidose", "Insulinpumpe", "insulinpflichtig", "insulinpfl", "insulinpf", "Insulin", "insulin", "IDMMII", "IDMII", "IDDMII", "IDDMI", "IDDM", "iDDM", "Gestationsdiabetes", "DMII", "dmii", "DMI", "Dm", "diabetisch", "Diabetes", "Diabet", "diabet", "Diab", "diab", "daib", "Diab.", "Diab", "diab.", "diab", "Diabetes", "diabetes", "DM", "dm", "niddm", "iddm", "Niddm", "lddm", "NIDDM", "IDDM", "Diabetiker", "Diabetikerin"

Kidney diseases	"Analgetikanephropathie", "Teilnephektomie", "Schrumpfnieren", "NTX", "Nierenversagen", "Nierentransplantation", "Nierentransplant", "Nierenteilinfarkt", "Nierenstein", "Niereninsuffizienz", "Niereninsuff", "Nierencysten", "Nierenarterienstenosis", "Nierenarterienstenose", "Nepropathie", "Nephrostomie", "Nephropathie", "Nephropat", "Nephrektomie", "Hämodialyse", "Einzelniere", "Einzelniere", "Dialysepflichtig", "dialysepflichtige", "dialysepflichtig", "Dialysepflicht", "Dialysepflichtige", "ANV", "CNI"
Lipoma	"Lipom", "Lipome", "lipom"
Lymphoedema	"Lymphorrhoe", "Lymphödem", "Lyphödem", "Lymphödeme", "Lymphödem", "LYMPHÖDEM", "Lymphöde", "Lymhödem", "lymhödem", "Lipolymphödem", "Sek. Lymphödem", "Lymphödem", "sek. Lymphödem", "lymphödem"
Melanoma	"Melanommetastase", "Melanomexstirpation", "Melanoma", "Melanom"
Mental, behavioral and neurodevelopmental disorders	"Schizophrenie", "schizotype", "Schizophrenie", "Schizophrenie", "schizoaffektive", "Riley", "Retardierung", "Retardierung", "psychot", "Psychosyndrom", "Psychosyndrom", "Psychose", "Persönlichkeitsstörung", "Oligophrenie", "neurokogn", "mentale", "Fremdkörperpsychose", "Depression", "Depressio", "depr", "konnatalen", "Geistige", "geistige", "Entwicklungsstörung", "Down", "ADHS", "Angststörung", "bipolare", "Bipolare", "Borderline", "Chairi"
Multidrug-resistant pathogen	"VRE", "MRSA", "Mrsa", "MRGN", "MRE", "Iwoff", "ESBL", "esbl", "3MRGN", "4MRGN", "A.baumannii", "A.Baumannii", "A.baumannii", "A.Baumannii", "A.baumannii", "A.Baumannii", "A.Baumannii", "A.baumannii", "Abaumannii", "ABaumannii", "Baumani", "baumani", "Baumannii", "Baumannii", "baumani", "baumani", "Baumannii"
Naevus	"melanozytärer", "Naevus", "Nävus", "naevus", "Muttermal", "muttermal"
Necrosis	"Zehenspitzennekrosen", "Zehenspitzennekrose", "Zehennekrosen", "Zehengruppennekrosen", "Spitzennekrose", "Plantarnekkrose", "nekrotisierender", "nekrotisierendem", "Nekrotisches", "nekrotisches", "nekrotischer", "nekrotische", "nekrotica", "Nekrot", "nekrot", "Nekroseplatte", "Nekrosen", "Nekrosektomie", "Nekrosekt", "Nekrosekotmie", "Nekrose", "Nekro", "Hüftkopfnekrose", "Hautnekrosen", "Hautnekrose", "Gaumennekrose", "Fettgewebnekrose", "Fersennekrose", "Nekrot.", "Nekrotische", "Nekrotisch", "nekrot.", "nekrotische", "nekrotisch"
Obesity	"Sleeve", "sleeve", "Magenverkleinerung", "Magenbypass", "Magenbypass", "Magenband", "Adipoistas", "Adipositas", "Adipos", "adipositas", "Adipositas", "Adipositas", "Adipositas", "Adipositas"
Oedema	"Schwellung", "Schwellung", "Stauungsdermatitis", "Stauungsödeme", "Stauungsdermatitis", "Stauungsdermatitis", "Stauungsdermatose", "Stauungsdermatitis", "Stauungsdermatitis", "Stauungs", "Stauungsdermatose", "Stauungsdermatitis", "Stauungsdermatitis", "Spannungsblasen", "Spannungsblase", "Spannungsblase", "Spannungsblase", "Spannungsblase", "Beimödem", "BEinödem", "Beinödeme", "BEinödeme", "Beinödemen", "BEinödemen", "Beinödeme"
Osteomyelitis	"Osteomyelitis", "Osteomeylitis", "Osteomyelitis", "Osteomyelitis", "Osteomyelitis", "Osteomyelitis", "Osteomyelitis", "Osteomyelitis", "Osteomyelitis", "Osteomyelitis"
Panniculitis	"Pannikulitis", "Panniculitis"
Paronychia	"Pan. dig III man sin.", "Parronychie", "PARonychie", "Paronychie", "Paronychia", "Panaritium", "Panaritium", "Panaritium", "nagelbett", "Nagelbett", "Nagelbettentz"
Peripheral arterial disease	"PTAs", "PTA's", "PTA", "Venenbypass", "Venebypass", "Kunststoffbypass", "Empbolektomie", "Embolektomie", "Embolektomie", "Crossoverbypass", "CLAudicatio", "Claudicatio", "Angiopathie", "Angiopathie", "Angiopathie", "FemPOP", "FemPop", "Fempop", "fempop", "fem.pop.Bypass", "fem.pop", "Veneninterponat", "Thrombendarteriektomie", "Thrombektomie", "TEA", "Stentverschluss", "STents", "Stents", "Stenting", "Stentin", "Stentimplantationen", "Stentimplantation", "Stentanlage", "Stentangioplastie", "Stent8", "STENT", "STent", "Stent", "stent", "Stenosen", "Stenosen", "STenose", "Stenose", "Stenos", "Revaskularisierung", "revask", "Prostvasin", "Profundapathplastik", "Profundapatchplastik", "POP", "POp", "Pop", "pOP", "pop", "PAVKL", "pAVKIV", "pAVK4", "PAVK", "PaVK", "Pavk", "paVK", "pavk",

	"PÄtschplastik", "PATCHplastik", "Patchplastik", "PATCH", "Patch", "mumifiziert", "Leriche", "Leistenrekonstruktion", "Leistenrekonstruktion", "Leistenrekonstruktion", "Leistenpatchplastik", "Leistengefäßrekonstruktion", "IVB", "IIIb", "IIa", "IIB", "IIb", "IIA", "IIa", "Fontaine", "Enderterektomie", "paVK", "PAVK", "pavk", "pAVK", "Pavk", "Abgagnsstenose", "Abgangverschluss", "ART", "arteriell", "arterielle", "arterieller", "arterielles", "Arterien", "Arterienstenose", "Arterienstenosen", "arteriosa", "Arteriosklerose", "arteriosum", "AV", "AVK", "Atherosklerose"
Plantar fasciitis	"Plantaraponeuritis"
Plantar wart	"Warzen", "Warze", "Dornwarze", "Dornwarzenexstirpation", "Verucca plantar sin"
Polyneuropathy	"polyneuropatisches", "Polyneuropathisches", "polyneuropathisches", "Polyneuropathie", "neurpath", "neurophat", "Neuroph", "neuroph", "Neuropathisches", "neuropathisches", "neuropathischen", "neuropathischem", "neuropathische", "neuropathisch", "Neuropathiesyndrom", "Neuropathie", "Neuropath", "neuropath", "neuropat", "Neurop", "neurop", "PNP", "pnp", "Polyneuropathie", "polyneuropathie"
Posttraumatic wound healing disorder	"Sturz mit Fahrrad", "Metallsplitter", "Splitter", "Schnittverletzung", "Motorradunfall", "VIs ind sin operat", "Glassplitter", "fragl FK", "Fremdkörper", "Corpora aliena", "Corpus alienum", "Hämatom", "Hämatompunktion", "Hämatomhöhle", "Hämatome", "Hämatomausräumung", "Hämatomausräumung", "Hämatom", "Hamätom", "haematoma", "Hämatom", "Hämatom", "hämatom", "Metallsplitter", "Eisensplitterverletzung", "Wunddehiszenz", "Wunddehiszenz", "Vulnc", "Vuln", "vuln", "Vollhautplastik", "VLC", "VIC", "Vic", "VKU", "Verletzung", "Verbrühung", "Verbrennungsunfall", "Verbrennung", "Verätzung", "Fraktur", "Überrolltrauma", "Traumatisches", "traumatisches", "traumatischer", "Traumatische", "traumatische", "traumatisch", "Traumat", "traumat", "Trauma", "Traum", "traum", "Stromunfall", "Spalttransplantation", "Spalthauttransplantation", "Spalthauttranspl", "Spalthautentnahmestelle", "Spalthautentnahme", "Spalthautdeckung", "Spalthaut", "Spaltdeckung", "Spaltaut", "Spalthauttransplantation", "Spalthautdeckung", "sciss", "scis", "Schussverletzung", "Schussverletzung", "Schürfwunde", "Schnittwunde", "Schnittverletzung", "RQW", "Rißquetschwunde", "Rissquetschwunde", "Quetschung", "Posttraumat", "posttraumat", "posttraumatische", "posttraumat", "posttraumatisches", "posttraumatischer", "posttraumat", "posttraumatische", "Posttraumatisch", "posttraumatisch", "Posttraumat", "posttraumat", "Posttraum", "posttraum", "Posttraumat", "posttraumat", "posttraumatisches", "Posttraumat", "posttraumat", "posttraum", "postoptraumat", "posstraumat", "Polytrauma", "Pfählungsverletzung", "nachTrauma", "Lappen", "Lappenplastik", "Kreissägenverletzung", "Kettensägeverletzung", "Explosionstrauma", "Entnahmestelle", "Enthnahmestelle", "Decollement", "Decollm", "Decollement", "Decoll", "Combutio", "Combusto", "Combustion", "Combustio", "Posttraumat. WHST", "posttraumat. WHST", "Posttraumatische WHST", "posttraumatische WHST", "Arbeitsunfall"
Pressure ulcer	"Sartoriuslappenplastik", "Sartoriuslappenpl", "Sakraldekubitus", "Sacraldekubitus", "Sacraldekubitus", "Glutealdekubitus", "Glutealdeku", "FErsendekubitus", "Fersendekubitus", "Fersendekubitud", "Fersendeku", "Fersendecubitus", "Fersendecubitus", "Druckkulkus", "Druckkulkus", "Druckkulcera", "Druckulc", "Dekutibus", "Dekubitus", "Dekubitalulzera", "Deku", "Dedcubitus", "Decubius", "Debubitus", "Decubitus", "Decubitus", "Decubitus", "Decubitus", "Decubitis", "Decubitis", "Decu", "Dekubits", "dekubitus", "decubitus", "Deku", "deku"
Pyoderma gangrenosum	"Pyoderma", "Pyod", "gang", "gangränosum"
Respiratory infection	"resp. Infekt"
Rheumatic and musculoskeletal diseases	"Rhizarthrose", "rheumt", "Rheumatoide", "rheumatoide", "rheumatischer", "rheumat", "Rheuma", "rheum", "Reumatoide", "psoriatica", "Polyarthrose", "Polyarthrit", "Muskelerkrankung", "Kollagenose", "Kollagenose", "Großzehengrundgelenksarthrose", "Gichtulcus", "Gichttophus", "Gichttophi", "Gichtfinger", "Gichtassoziertes", "Gichtassoz", "Gicht", "Formenkreis", "ankolysierende", "Arhritis", "Arthrose", "arthrit", "Arthritis", "Athritis", "Athrose", "Bechterev", "Bechterew", "Arthrose"

Squamous cell carcinoma	"PlepCA", "PlepCa", "PLEP", "Plep", "Plattenepithelcarcinoms", "Plattenepithelcarcinom", "PlattenepithelCA", "Plattenepithel", "Platenepithel"
Suture granuloma	"Schloffer", "Granulom", "Fadengraunolom", "Fadengranumlom", "Fadengranulom", "Fadengranulmrevision"
Tenosynovitis	"Tendovaginitis"
Thrombophlebitis	"Thrombophlebitis"
Tumor diseases	"vesicae", "LeberTU", "CUP", "CML", "Bronchus", "Adeno", "Whipple", "Wertheim", "Weichteiltumor", "Weichteilsarkom", "Vulvakarzinom", "UrothelCA", "Tumorektomie", "Tumor", "TU", "Tu", "Teratom", "TACE", "Stammzellentransplant", "SBB", "Sarkom", "RFA", "RektumCA", "Radiofrequenzabl", "Radiochemotherapie", "Radiochemo", "Radio", "Radiatio", "R0", "R1", "pT4", "pT3", "pT1", "Prostatacarcinom", "ProstataCA", "ProstataCa", "Postchemo", "Pleurakarzinom", "PankreasCA", "Pancreaslinksresektion", "Pancreaskopfresektion", "Pancreas", "pancreas", "Peritonealkarzinose", "Parotistumor", "Paraganlion", "ovaril", "NiernzellCA", "Niernzellcarcinom", "Niernzell", "NierenTu", "NierenCell", "Nierncell", "NierenCA", "Neurom", "Neuroendokr", "Neurinom", "neoadj", "Nebennierenadenom", "Neckdissection", "N.Mammae", "N.mammae", "Myxofibrosarcom", "Myelom", "metastasiertes", "Metastasiertes", "metast", "Meningiom", "Meningeom", "Mastektomie", "Mammatumor", "Mammakarzinom", "maligner", "maligna", "Lymphom", "Leukämie", "Leiomyosarkom", "Leiomyomsarkom", "Kleinhirntumor", "Keratoakanthom", "IPMN", "invasives", "Hypophysenadenom", "Hodkin", "Hodgkin", "Gebärmutterhalskrebs", "exulceriertes", "exulcerierter", "Exulcerierte", "exulcerierender", "Exulc", "exulc", "Darmkrebs", "ColonCa", "CLL", "Cholangioz", "ChemoTherapie", "Chemotherapie", "Chemoinduz", "chemoinduz", "Chemoembolisation", "Chemo", "Carcinosis", "Carcinoseileus", "Carcinobelastung", "Carcinom", "Exulc.", "Exulz.", "exulc.", "exulz.", "AdenoCA", "AnalCa", "AscendensCA", "Astrocytom", "Bestrahlung", "BlasenCA", "Bowen", "BronchusCA", "Burkitt", "CA", "Sertolizelltumor"
Ulcer	"Miniulcus", "Wunde", "Wunden", "Ulzerosa", "Ulzera", "ulzera", "Ulucs", "Ulkusw", "Ulkus", "Ulkus", "Ulklus", "Ulkiusw", "Ulkius", "Ulkcus", "Ulkc", "Ulkius", "Ulera", "Ulcusblutung", "ULcus", "Ulcus", "ulcus", "Ulcuc", "Ulcu", "Ulcrs", "Ulcfera", "Ulces", "Ulcers", "ulceröse", "ulcerose", "ulcerosa", "Ulcerer", "Ulcere", "Ulcerationen", "ulcerationen", "Ulceration", "Ulceraq", "ULcera", "Ulcera", "ulcera", "Ulcer", "ULcc", "Ulcc", "Ulc.crur", "ULc", "Ulc", "Ulilus", "Ulilus", "Ucus", "Strahlenulcus", "Stauungsulcus", "Spitzenulcus", "Rezidivulcus", "Präulcus", "Präulcus", "präulceröse", "präulc", "Präukus", "Praelculus", "Plantarulcus", "plantarulcus", "Nabelgrubenulcus", "Nabelgrube", "Mikroulcerationen", "Mikroulcera", "Manschettenulcus", "Manschettenulcera", "Manschettenulc", "Manchettenuklus", "Manchettenuklus", "Lymphfistel", "Lagerungsschaden", "Lagerungsschade", "Gamaschenulcus", "Gamaschenulcus", "Gamaschenulcus", "Gamaschenulcera", "Fersenulcus", "Fersenulkus", "cururis", "curur", "curuis", "curis", "cura", "cur", "cruris", "Cruis", "cruris", "cruraler", "cruralem", "crura", "Cru", "crur", "Ulcus cruris", "Ulc. crur.", "Ulcera", "Ulcc.crur", "Ulc. dig.", "Ulc. ped.", "Ulcus AK", "Ulc. plant", "Ulc. man.", "Ulcus mal.", "Ulcus plantar", "ulcus cruris", "ulc. crur.", "ulcera", "ulcc.crur", "ulc. dig.", "ulc. ped.", "ulcus AK", "ulc. plant", "ulc. man.", "ulcus mal.", "ulcus plantar", "abszed. Ulcus", "Abszed.", "Ulkus", "ulkus", "Ulkc.", "ulk.", "Ulcus", "ulcus", "Subung. Ulcus", "Subung. Ulc.", "subung. ulcus", "subung. ulc."
Unguis incarnatus	"incart", "incarnatus", "incarn", "Incarc", "incarc", "inca", "Emmert", "Emmertplastik", "Ung. Inc", "ung. inc.", "Unguis", "unguis", "ung.inc.re", "UNg", "Ung", "ung"
Vasculitis	"Vaskulitis", "Vasculitis", "Thrombangitis", "Schönlein", "Riesenzellarteritis", "obliterans", "Livedovasculitis", "leukozytoplastische", "Leukozytoklastische", "Leukozytoklast", "Henoch", "Henoch", "Autoimmunvasculitis"
Wart	"Warzen", "Warze", "Dornwarze", "Dornwarzenexstirpation", "Verucca plantar sin"
Dependence on Wheelchair	"Paraparese", "Hemiparese", "Spastische", "Rolli", "Rollstuhl", "Querschnittslähmung", "Querschnittläsion", "Querschnittlähmung", "Querschnitt", "Tetraplegie", "Tetraparese", "Myelomeningocele"

Additional file 4: Assignment of diagnoses to the main chapters of the ICD-11

The table below shows selected ICD-11 main chapters in the left column, alongside the corresponding diagnostic categories or specific diagnoses identified from the EHRs through an NLP process.

Table 1. ICD-11 main chapters and corresponding EHR-derived diagnoses and diagnostic categories

Assignment of diagnoses to the main chapters of the ICD-11		
1	Certain infectious or parasitic diseases	Erysipelas
2	Neoplasms	Tumour diseases
5	Endocrine, nutritional or metabolic diseases	Diabetes mellitus Obesity
6	Mental, behavioural or neurodevelopmental disorders	Alcohol and substance use disorders Dementia Mental, behavioural or neurodevelopmental disorders
11	Diseases of the circulatory system	Cardiovascular diseases Lymphoedema Thrombophlebitis
14	Diseases of the skin	Delayed healing of surgical wound of skin
15	Diseases of the musculoskeletal system or connective tissue	Compartment syndrome Osteomyelitis Rheumatic and musculoskeletal diseases
16	Diseases of the genitourinary system	Kidney diseases
21	Symptoms, signs or clinical findings, not elsewhere classified	Multidrug-resistant pathogen Necrosis Oedema Gangrene
22	Injury, poisoning or certain other consequences of external causes	Post-traumatic wound healing disorder
24	Factors influencing health status or contact with health services	Dependence on wheelchair Amputation

Additional file 5. STROBE flow chart of the study population

The Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) flow chart, shows the study population from the outpatient wound clinic. The original study population consisted of 5,137 patients. Patients were excluded from the study if they were not undergoing treatment (n = 384), if the information provided related exclusively to laboratory referrals, test results, or prescriptions, or if no information about diagnosis was available (n = 33). Patients who received only one or more of the following diagnoses*: Anorectal conditions (i.e. Haemorrhoids or Anal fissures), Animal-related injuries, Bursitis, Carbuncle, Carpal tunnel syndrome, Clavus, Condyloma, Cosmetic Procedures, Eczema, Epidermoid Cyst, Exanthema, Fibroma, Fistula, Foot Malalignment, Infection of unknown origin, Furuncle, Ganglion, Gastritis, Haemangioma, Heel spur, Hernia, Hidradenitis suppurativa, Intertrigo, Keloid, Lipoma, Naevus, Paronychia, Plantar fasciitis, Plantar wart, Respiratory Infection, Suture Granuloma, Tenosynovitis, Thrombophlebitis, Unguis incarnatus have been excluded (n = 284) as well as patients under the age of 18 (n = 177). The exclusion criteria were established prior to classifying comorbidities using the main chapters of ICD-11. Patients who did not have at least one of the following chronic wound diagnoses: arteriovenous ulcer, chronic peripheral venous insufficiency of lower extremities, diabetic foot syndrome, chronic arterial occlusive disease, pressure ulcer, atypical wounds, and/or an ulcer (n = 412) have also been excluded. A total of 3,847 patients met the inclusion criteria and were used for the analysis.

Figure 1. STROBE flow chart

Additional file 6. STROBE Statement

Checklist of items that should be included in reports of observational studies

	Item No	Recommendation	Implementation
Title and abstract	1	(a) Indicate the study's design with a commonly used term in the title or the abstract (b) Provide in the abstract an informative and balanced summary of what was done and what was found	The study design is included in the title. The abstract includes background, methods, results and conclusions.
Introduction			
Background/rationale	2	Explain the scientific background and rationale for the investigation being reported	Explained in the background.
Objectives	3	State specific objectives, including any prespecified hypotheses	Explained in the background.
Methods			
Study design	4	Present key elements of study design early in the paper	Described in the methods.
Setting	5	Describe the setting, locations, and relevant dates, including periods of recruitment, exposure, follow-up, and data collection	Described in the methods and results section and Additional file 5 and 6.
Participants	6	(a) <i>Cohort study</i> —Give the eligibility criteria, and the sources and methods of selection of participants. Describe methods of follow-up <i>Case-control study</i> —Give the eligibility criteria, and the sources and methods of case ascertainment and control selection. Give the rationale for the choice of cases and controls <i>Cross-sectional study</i> —Give the eligibility criteria, and the sources and methods of selection of participants	Described in the methods section and Additional file 5 and 6.
		(b) <i>Cohort study</i> —For matched studies, give matching criteria and number of exposed and unexposed <i>Case-control study</i> —For matched studies, give matching criteria and the number of controls per case	NA
Variables	7	Clearly define all outcomes, exposures, predictors, potential confounders, and effect modifiers. Give diagnostic criteria, if applicable	Included in the methods section and Additional file 3, 4 and 12.
Data sources/measurement	8*	For each variable of interest, give sources of data and details of methods of assessment (measurement). Describe comparability of assessment methods if there is more than one group	Described in the methods and results section and Additional file 7 to 15.
Bias	9	Describe any efforts to address potential sources of bias	Described in the discussion.
Study size	10	Explain how the study size was arrived at	Described in the results section and Additional file 5 and 6.
Quantitative variables	11	Explain how quantitative variables were handled in the analyses. If applicable, describe which groupings were chosen and why	Explained in the methods section.

Statistical methods	12	(a) Describe all statistical methods, including those used to control for confounding	Described in the methods and results section and Additional file 11 and 15.
		(b) Describe any methods used to examine subgroups and interactions	Described in the methods and results section and Additional file 6, 11, 12 and 15.
		(c) Explain how missing data were addressed	Described in Additional file 5.
		(d) <i>Cohort study</i> —If applicable, explain how loss to follow-up was addressed <i>Case-control study</i> —If applicable, explain how matching of cases and controls was addressed <i>Cross-sectional study</i> —If applicable, describe analytical methods taking account of sampling strategy	NA
		(e) Describe any sensitivity analyses	Described in Additional file 11 and 15.
Results			
Participants	13*	(a) Report numbers of individuals at each stage of study—eg numbers potentially eligible, examined for eligibility, confirmed eligible, included in the study, completing follow-up, and analysed	Described in the results section and Additional file 5.
		(b) Give reasons for non-participation at each stage	NA
		(c) Consider use of a flow diagram	See Additional file 5.
Descriptive data	14*	(a) Give characteristics of study participants (eg demographic, clinical, social) and information on exposures and potential confounders	Described in the results section and Additional file 5 to 8, 10 and 13.
		(b) Indicate number of participants with missing data for each variable of interest	Described in results section and Additional file 5.
		(c) <i>Cohort study</i> —Summarise follow-up time (eg, average and total amount)	NA
Outcome data	15*	<i>Cohort study</i> —Report numbers of outcome events or summary measures over time	NA
		<i>Case-control study</i> —Report numbers in each exposure category, or summary measures of exposure	NA
		<i>Cross-sectional study</i> —Report numbers of outcome events or summary measures	NA
Main results	16	(a) Give unadjusted estimates and, if applicable, confounder-adjusted estimates and their precision (eg, 95% confidence interval). Make clear which confounders were adjusted for and why they were included	NA
		(b) Report category boundaries when continuous variables were categorized	Reported in the results section and Additional file 8 and 13.
		(c) If relevant, consider translating estimates of relative risk into absolute risk for a meaningful time period	NA
Other analyses	17	Report other analyses done—eg analyses of subgroups and interactions, and sensitivity analyses	Reported in the results section and Additional file 11 and 15. Methods used to analyse the data included descriptive statistics and graphical

depictions (e.g. box plots and bar charts).

Discussion			
Key results	18	Summarise key results with reference to study objectives	Described in the discussion.
Limitations	19	Discuss limitations of the study, taking into account sources of potential bias or imprecision. Discuss both direction and magnitude of any potential bias	Described in the discussion.
Interpretation	20	Give a cautious overall interpretation of results considering objectives, limitations, multiplicity of analyses, results from similar studies, and other relevant evidence	Described in the discussion.
Generalisability	21	Discuss the generalisability (external validity) of the study results	Described in the discussion.
Other information			
Funding	22	Give the source of funding and the role of the funders for the present study and, if applicable, for the original study on which the present article is based	Included at the end of the manuscript.

*Give information separately for cases and controls in case-control studies and, if applicable, for exposed and unexposed groups in cohort and cross-sectional studies.

Note: An Explanation and Elaboration article discusses each checklist item and gives methodological background and published examples of transparent reporting. The STROBE checklist is best used in conjunction with this article (freely available on the Web sites of PLoS Medicine at <http://www.plosmedicine.org/>, Annals of Internal Medicine at <http://www.annals.org/>, and Epidemiology at <http://www.epidem.com/>). Information on the STROBE Initiative is available at www.strobe-statement.org.

Additional file 7. Sensitivity analysis of sex differences in sample characteristics

This table presents a sensitivity analysis focusing on sex-specific baseline differences, excluding patients under 70 years old.

Table 1. Sample Characteristics for population >70 years. Significant differences are marked in red.

Characteristics	All (n = 2037) n (%), 95% CI)	Female (n = 1081) n (%), 95% CI)	Male (n = 956) n (%), 95% CI)	p-value
Age in years (Md, IQR)	80 [76 to 85]	81 [77 to 86]	79 [75 to 83]	<0.001
Age in years (M, \pm SD)	80.67 (\pm 6.39)	81.67 (\pm 6.67)	79.53 (\pm 5.85)	<0.001
Aetiology of chronic wound				
Arteriovenous ulcer	150 (7.4, 6.3-8.6)	81 (7.5, 6.0-9.2)	69 (7.2, 5.7-9.0)	0.876
CVI*	310 (15.2, 13.7-16.9)	197 (18.2, 16.0-20.7)	113 (11.8, 9.8-14.0)	<0.001
Diabetic foot syndrome	282 (13.8, 12.4-15.4)	123 (11.4, 9.5-13.4)	159 (16.6, 14.3-19.1)	0.001
Chronic arterial occlusive disease without CVI	454 (22.3, 20.5-24.2)	173 (16.0, 13.9-18.3)	281 (29.4, 26.5-32.4)	<0.001
Pressure ulcer	299 (14.7, 13.2-16.3)	159 (14.7, 12.6-17.0)	140 (14.6, 12.5-17.0)	1.000
Atypical wounds	107 (5.3, 4.3-6.3)	47 (4.3, 3.2-5.7)	60 (6.3, 4.8-8.0)	0.065
Comorbidities according to ICD-11				
Certain infectious or parasitic diseases	172 (8.4, 7.3-9.7)	86 (8.0, 6.4-9.7)	86 (9.0, 7.3-11.0)	0.446
Neoplasms	231 (11.3, 10.0-12.8)	108 (10.0, 8.3-11.9)	123 (12.9, 10.8-15.2)	0.049
Endocrine, nutritional or metabolic diseases	974 (47.8, 45.6-50.0)	458 (42.4, 39.4-45.4)	516 (54.0, 50.8-57.2)	<0.001
MBND**	64 (3.1, 2.4-4.0)	36 (3.3, 2.3-4.6)	28 (2.9, 2.0-4.2)	0.696
Diseases of the circulatory system	733 (36.0, 33.9-38.1)	341 (31.5, 28.8-34.4)	392 (41.0, 37.9-44.2)	<0.001
Diseases of the musculo-skeletal system***	132 (6.5, 5.4-7.6)	55 (5.1, 3.9-6.6)	77 (8.1, 6.4-10.0)	0.009
Diseases of the genitourinary system	166 (8.1, 7.0-9.4)	72 (6.7, 5.2-8.3)	94 (9.8, 8.0-11.9)	0.011
Injuries, symptoms, signs or clinical findings				
...Delayed healing of surgical wound of skin	149 (7.3, 6.2-8.5)	67 (6.2, 4.8-7.8)	82 (8.6, 6.9-10.5)	0.048
Diabetes mellitus	960 (47.1, 44.9-49.3)	450 (41.6, 38.7-44.6)	510 (53.3, 50.1-56.5)	<0.001
Gangrene	115 (5.6, 4.7-6.7)	37 (3.4, 2.4-4.7)	78 (8.2, 6.5-10.1)	<0.001
Multidrug-resistant pathogen	265 (13.0, 11.6-14.5)	124 (11.5, 9.6-13.5)	141 (14.7, 12.6-17.2)	0.033
Necrosis	630 (30.9, 28.9-33.0)	302 (27.9, 25.3-30.7)	328 (34.3, 31.3-37.4)	0.002
Oedema	536 (26.3, 24.4-28.3)	277 (25.6, 23.0-28.3)	259 (27.1, 24.3-30.0)	0.484
Polyneuropathy	475 (23.3, 21.5-25.2)	197 (18.2, 16.0-20.6)	278 (29.1, 26.2-32.1)	<0.001
...Posttraumatic impaired wound healing	560 (27.5, 25.6-29.5)	294 (27.2, 24.6-30.0)	266 (27.8, 25.0-30.8)	0.790

Factors influencing health status

Amputation	233 (11.4, 10.1-12.9)	82 (7.6, 6.1-9.3)	151 (15.8, 13.5-18.3)	<0.001
Dependence on wheelchair	41 (2.0, 1.4-2.7)	14 (1.3, 0.7-2.2)	27 (2.8, 1.9-4.1)	0.022

* Chronic peripheral venous insufficiency of lower extremities without chronic arterial occlusive disease, ** Mental, behavioural or neurodevelopmental disorders, *** or connective tissue

Additional file 8. Numerical breakdown of visit distribution

Table 1 shows the visit frequency across age groups and sexes for the entire study population (n = 3847). Table 2 details the visit frequency by age and sex specifically for patients with a healed outcome (n = 1808).

Table 1. Visit distribution by age group and sex within the entire study population

Age group	Number of visits	Female (n = 1840)	Male (n = 2007)
≤20	1–25	7 (0.38)	5 (0.25)
≤20	26–50	1 (0.05)	1 (0.05)
≤20	>100	-	1 (0.05)
21–25	1–25	19 (1.03)	20 (1.00)
21–25	26–50	2 (0.11)	4 (0.20)
26–30	1–25	26 (1.41)	23 (1.15)
26–30	26–50	4 (0.22)	2 (0.10)
26–30	51–75	-	1 (0.05)
26–30	76–100	1 (0.05)	-
26–30	>100	2 (0.11)	1 (0.05)
31–35	1–25	29 (1.58)	39 (1.94)
31–35	26–50	4 (0.22)	6 (0.30)
31–35	51–75	1 (0.05)	2 (0.10)
31–35	76–100	2 (0.11)	-
36–40	1–25	36 (1.96)	33 (1.64)
36–40	26–50	6 (0.33)	4 (0.20)
36–40	51–75	4 (0.22)	6 (0.30)
36–40	76–100	-	1 (0.05)
36–40	>100	1 (0.05)	6 (0.30)
41–45	1–25	35 (1.90)	32 (1.59)
41–45	26–50	5 (0.27)	1 (0.05)
41–45	51–75	3 (0.16)	6 (0.30)
41–45	76–100	1 (0.05)	7 (0.35)
41–45	>100	3 (0.16)	12 (0.60)
46–50	1–25	37 (2.01)	37 (1.84)
46–50	26–50	16 (0.87)	19 (0.95)
46–50	51–75	3 (0.16)	4 (0.20)
46–50	76–100	2 (0.11)	4 (0.20)
46–50	>100	4 (0.22)	12 (0.60)
51–55	1–25	68 (3.70)	71 (3.54)
51–55	26–50	16 (0.87)	23 (1.15)
51–55	51–75	3 (0.16)	11 (0.55)
51–55	76–100	3 (0.16)	8 (0.40)
51–55	>100	5 (0.27)	20 (1.00)

56-60	1-25	74 (4.02)	100 (4.98)
56-60	26-50	19 (1.03)	44 (2.19)
56-60	51-75	11 (0.60)	23 (1.15)
56-60	76-100	5 (0.27)	8 (0.40)
56-60	>100	16 (0.87)	41 (2.04)
61-65	1-25	82 (4.46)	120 (5.98)
61-65	26-50	32 (1.74)	43 (2.14)
61-65	51-75	8 (0.43)	24 (1.20)
61-65	76-100	5 (0.27)	9 (0.45)
61-65	>100	10 (0.54)	33 (1.64)
66-70	1-25	84 (4.57)	87 (4.33)
66-70	26-50	34 (1.85)	40 (1.99)
66-70	51-75	13 (0.71)	17 (0.85)
66-70	76-100	6 (0.33)	11 (0.55)
66-70	>100	11 (0.60)	29 (1.44)
71-75	1-25	131 (7.12)	129 (6.43)
71-75	26-50	41 (2.23)	62 (3.09)
71-75	51-75	24 (1.30)	30 (1.49)
71-75	76-100	9 (0.49)	11 (0.55)
71-75	>100	18 (0.98)	37 (1.84)
76-80	1-25	162 (8.80)	153 (7.62)
76-80	26-50	59 (3.21)	66 (3.29)
76-80	51-75	29 (1.58)	35 (1.74)
76-80	76-100	17 (0.92)	18 (0.90)
76-80	>100	26 (1.41)	33 (1.64)
81-85	1-25	166 (9.02)	143 (7.13)
81-85	26-50	66 (3.59)	42 (2.09)
81-85	51-75	17 (0.92)	19 (0.95)
81-85	76-100	14 (0.76)	8 (0.40)
81-85	>100	9 (0.49)	6 (0.30)
86-90	1-25	108 (5.87)	83 (4.14)
86-90	26-50	25 (1.36)	19 (0.95)
86-90	51-75	11 (0.60)	6 (0.30)
86-90	76-100	10 (0.54)	3 (0.15)
86-90	>100	7 (0.38)	6 (0.30)
91-95	1-25	76 (4.13)	31 (1.54)
91-95	26-50	26 (1.41)	6 (0.30)
91-95	51-75	6 (0.33)	1 (0.05)
91-95	76-100	1 (0.05)	2 (0.10)
91-95	>100	3 (0.16)	2 (0.10)
96-100	1-25	12 (0.65)	5 (0.25)
96-100	26-50	3 (0.16)	-
96-100	51-75	1 (0.05)	-
>100	1-25	4 (0.22)	-

Table 2. Visit distribution by age group and sex within patients with a healed outcome

Age group	Number of visits	Female (n = 803)	Male (n = 1005)
≤20	1–25	3 (0.37)	1 (0.10)
≤20	26–50	1 (0.12)	1 (0.10)
≤20	>100	-	1 (0.10)
21–25	1–25	5 (0.62)	3 (0.30)
21–25	26–50	2 (0.25)	2 (0.20)
26–30	1–25	7 (0.87)	10 (1.0)
26–30	26–50	2 (0.25)	1 (0.10)
26–30	51–75	-	1 (0.10)
26–30	76–100	1 (0.12)	-
26–30	>100	2 (0.25)	1 (0.10)
31–35	1–25	10 (1.25)	10 (1.00)
31–35	26–50	1 (0.12)	4 (0.40)
31–35	51–75	2 (0.25)	2 (0.20)
31–35	76–100	2 (0.25)	-
36–40	1–25	9 (1.12)	14 (1.39)
36–40	26–50	1 (0.12)	2 (0.20)
36–40	51–75	1 (0.12)	5 (0.50)
36–40	76–100	-	1 (0.10)
36–40	>100	1 (0.12)	6 (0.60)
41–45	1–25	12 (1.49)	15 (1.49)
41–45	26–50	4 (0.50)	-
41–45	51–75	2 (0.25)	4 (0.40)
41–45	76–100	1 (0.12)	6 (0.60)
41–45	>100	3 (0.37)	8 (0.80)
46–50	1–25	12 (1.49)	15 (1.49)
46–50	26–50	12 (1.49)	11 (1.09)
46–50	51–75	2 (0.25)	3 (0.30)
46–50	76–100	2 (0.25)	4 (0.40)
46–50	>100	4 (0.50)	9 (0.90)
51–55	1–25	16 (1.99)	26 (2.59)
51–55	26–50	8 (1.00)	13 (1.29)
51–55	51–75	2 (0.25)	7 (0.70)
51–55	76–100	3 (0.37)	6 (0.60)
51–55	>100	4 (0.50)	17 (1.69)
56–60	1–25	23 (2.86)	38 (3.78)
56–60	26–50	10 (1.25)	27 (2.69)
56–60	51–75	3 (0.37)	15 (1.49)
56–60	76–100	4 (0.50)	5 (0.50)
56–60	>100	15 (1.87)	35 (3.48)
61–65	1–25	31 (3.86)	48 (4.78)
61–65	26–50	18 (2.24)	24 (2.39)
61–65	51–75	5 (0.62)	19 (1.89)
61–65	76–100	4 (0.50)	6 (0.60)
61–65	>100	8 (1.00)	30 (2.99)
66–70	1–25	28 (3.49)	24 (2.39)

66-70	26-50	13 (1.62)	18 (1.79)
66-70	51-75	8 (1.00)	12 (1.19)
66-70	76-100	2 (0.25)	9 (0.90)
66-70	>100	10 (1.25)	24 (2.39)
71-75	1-25	38 (4.73)	48 (4.78)
71-75	26-50	21 (2.62)	38 (3.78)
71-75	51-75	13 (1.62)	20 (1.99)
71-75	76-100	5 (0.62)	8 (0.80)
71-75	>100	14 (1.75)	29 (2.89)
76-80	1-25	62 (7.72)	61 (6.07)
76-80	26-50	28 (3.49)	31 (3.08)
76-80	51-75	19 (2.37)	19 (1.89)
76-80	76-100	11 (1.37)	14 (1.39)
76-80	>100	23 (2.86)	29 (2.89)
81-85	1-25	61 (7.60)	51 (7.13)
81-85	26-50	39 (4.86)	19 (1.89)
81-85	51-75	13 (1.62)	12 (1.19)
81-85	76-100	8 (1.00)	6 (0.60)
81-85	>100	8 (1.00)	6 (0.60)
86-90	1-25	36 (4.48)	30 (2.99)
86-90	26-50	18 (2.24)	11 (1.09)
86-90	51-75	7 (0.87)	4 (0.40)
86-90	76-100	9 (1.12)	1 (0.10)
86-90	>100	7 (0.87)	5 (0.50)
91-95	1-25	18 (2.24)	12 (1.19)
91-95	26-50	14 (1.74)	2 (0.20)
91-95	51-75	6 (0.75)	1 (0.10)
91-95	76-100	-	1 (0.10)
91-95	>100	2 (0.25)	2 (0.20)
96-100	1-25	2 (0.25)	2 (0.20)
96-100	26-50	2 (0.25)	-
96-100	51-75	1 (0.12)	-
>100	1-25	1 (0.12)	-

Additional file 9. Sensitivity analysis of visit distribution by age group and sex among patients with a healed outcome

This stacked bar chart presents a sensitivity analysis focusing on the relative frequencies of patient visits to the outpatient wound clinic by age group and sex. The bar chart illustrates the relative frequencies of patient visits for individuals with a healed outcome (n = 1808) and demonstrates that our findings are robust against unmeasured confounding factors. A healed outcome refers to patients whose EHRs contain at least one of the following terms identified through the keyword matching algorithm: 'inAbheilung', 'Heilung', 'abgeheilt', 'Abgeheilt', or 'abgeheiltes'.

Figure 7. Visit distribution in patients with a healed outcome

The visits of all patients who met the inclusion criteria are listed below for comparison.

Figure 8. Visit distribution across the entire study population